

AUTOMATED VOTERS VERIFICATION SYSTEM THROUGH FACIAL RECOGNITION

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Abstract:

The automated voter verification system using face recognition aims to replace the manual verification of citizens during electoral polling. This system was designed with the objective to automatically identify each individual who votes, by capturing images and comparing the image with stored database image files. Extraction methods viz. PCA (Principal Component Analysis) –Thus we create a feature set for each of the images provided in the database. During real time, the images of human face may be extracted from a USB camera. The system will generate an internal list of the voters and non-voters during election. Better accuracy is attained in results and the system takes into account the changes that occurs in the face over the period of time. This system will reduce human efforts and also time required to verify the voters individually and also to eradicate the fraudulent voting. This paper will first audit the related works in the field of participation administration and face acknowledgment.

Key Words: Skin Classification, Image Acquisition, PCA, Eigenfaces, Open CV, Face Detection & Face Recognition.

Introduction:

Voter's identification and authentication techniques are essential for more secure platform mechanisms to overcome vulnerabilities of the client used by the voter to cast their vote. The verification is with an offline tool hence, we proposed an authentication technique using a Face Detection and Recognition system to achieve the rules of Supreme Electoral Council as follow: Only eligible persons vote, No person gets to vote more than once. To achieve this aims as follow: increase participation and improve the accuracy of results. In general, an FDR system starts by Interfacing with an image source for grabbing facial images, Automatic detection or manual selection of human face may be found within the scene, Manipulate (create, add, delete) a database of faces, Launching the recognition process by comparing the face previously detected with the database's faces. The proposed algorithms (Eigenface, PCA) are used here. Facial recognition or face recognition as it is often referred to as, analyses characteristics of a person's face image input through a camera. It measures overall facial structure, distances between eyes, nose, mouth, and jaw edges. These measurements are retained in a database and used as a comparison when a user stands before the camera. One of the strongest positive aspects of facial recognition is that it is non-intrusive. Verification or identification can be accomplished from two feet away or more, without requiring the user to wait for long periods of time or do anything more than look at the camera. The proposed system consists of a high resolution digital camera, The data or images obtained by the camera are sent to a computer programmed system for further analysis. The obtained images are then compared with a set of reference images of each of the voters. The camera module can be a wireless or wired system.

PCA Approach to Face Recognition:

The first notable and accepted descriptions of Principal Component Analysis were given in the early 20th century by Pearson and Hotelling [1]. Originally, the purpose of deriving principal components was to reduce the number of variables while still retaining pertinent information. This is particularly useful when the number of variables can be reduced significantly to a few principal components, even if the principal components have no clear meaning. The principal components provide vectors that describe the major variation of a sample. Oftentimes, severe reduction in dimensionality alone is justification for use of principal components, and can greatly enhance computational efficiency. Principal component analysis transforms a set of data obtained from possibly correlated variables into a set of values of uncorrelated variables called principal components. The number of components can be less than or equal to the number of original variables. The first principal component has the highest possible

Fig 1: Block Diagram of face recognition system

variance, and each of the succeeding component has the highest possible variance under the restriction that it has to be orthogonal to the previous component. We want to find the principal components, in this case eigenvectors of the covariance matrix of facial images. The first thing we need to do is to form a training data set. 2D image I_i can be represented as a 1D vector by concatenating rows [2]. Image is transformed into a vector of length $N = mn$.

$$I = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{m1} & x_{m2} & \dots & x_{mn} \end{bmatrix}_{m \times n} \xrightarrow{\text{CONCATENATION}} \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} \\ \vdots \\ x_{1n} \\ \vdots \\ x_{2n} \\ \vdots \\ x_{mn} \end{bmatrix}_{1 \times N} = X.$$

Let M such vectors x_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, M$) of length N form a matrix of learning images, X . To ensure that the first principal component describes the direction of maximum variance, it is necessary to center the matrix. First we determine the vector of mean values Ψ , and then subtract that vector from each image vector.

$$\Psi = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M x_i,$$

$$\Phi_i = x_i - \Psi.$$

The MATLAB section consists of the face recognition module. Face Recognition module- Initially the images of each of the users is provided for the MATLAB & generate a set of facial features using of the feature Extraction methods viz. PCA (Principal Component Analysis) –Thus we create a feature set for each of the images provided in the database. During real time, the images of human face may be extracted from a USB camera. This involves MATLAB's Image Acquisition Toolbox, using which a camera is configured, accessed & brought one frame at a time into MATLAB's workspace for further processing using MATLAB's Image Processing Toolbox. This method uses Eigen face approach for face recognition which was introduced by Kirby and Sirovich in 1988 at Brown University. The method works by analysing face images and computing eigenface which are faces composed of eigenvectors. The comparison of eigenface is used to identify the presence of a face and its identity. There is a five step process involved with the system developed by Turk and Pentland. First, the system needs to be initialized by feeding it a set of training images of faces. This is used to define the face space which is set of images that are face like. Next, when a face is encountered it calculates an eigenface for it. By comparing it with known faces and using some statistical analysis it can be determined whether the image presented is a face at all.

Related Work:

In related research, several voter identification and authentication techniques were introduced to secure voting platforms and overcome fake voting. "Identity Authentication" generally involves two stages: the first is Face Detection and Recognition, where a photo is searched to find any face in it. Next, an image processing algorithm is applied to clean up the facial image for easier recognition. The second stage is Face Matching, where the detected face is compared to an image retrieved from the SCE database using a national ID#. A matching algorithm is applied to verify the person for both matching.

The principal components of the distribution of faces or the eigenvectors of the covariance matrix of the set of face images, treating an image as a point (vector) in a very high dimensional face space is sought. Here principal component analysis method will be presented in more detail. The proposed system is based on an information theory approach that decomposes face images into a small set of characteristic feature images called „Eigen faces“, which are actually the principal components of the initial training set of face images. Recognition is performed by projecting a new image into the subspace spanned by the Eigen faces („face space“) and then classifying the face by comparing its position in the face space with the positions of the known individuals. The Eigen face approach gives us efficient way to find this lower dimensional space. Eigen faces are the Eigenvectors which are representative of each of the dimensions of this face space and they can be considered as various face features. Any face can be expressed as linear combinations of the singular vectors of the set of faces, and these singular vectors are eigenvectors of the covariance matrices. The Eigenface technique uses much more information by classifying faces based on general facial patterns. These patterns include, but are not limited to, the specific features of the face. Eigenface can be related directly to one of the most fundamental concepts in electrical engineering: Fourier analysis. Eigenface system needs a database of known faces in which all images are the same size (in pixels), and grayscale, with values ranging from 0 to 255. Each face image is converted into a vector of length N (where, $N = \text{image width} * \text{image height}$). We will use The ORL Database of Faces (AT&T database). This database contains 400 pictures of 40 subjects. A preview image of the Database of Faces. The output of the Eigenfaces system is the first point extraction of the person’s face which we will be used to verify the voter’s identity. The voter will enter his ID number which is used to fetch his image from SCE data base this image will be considered as the first point. The voter’s image captured using a webcam is the input to the Eigenface system to detect the face from image and this will be the second point. The two points are checked for matching using pattern matching algorithm.

Analysis:

And the average image, call it Ψ_f is

$$\Psi_f = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \Gamma_i$$

we compute the collection of each face minus the mean, call it A_f .

$$A_f = [\Phi_1, \Phi_2, \dots, \Phi_M]_{16384 \times 10}$$

Future Scope:

The current recognition system has been designed for frontal views of face images. A neural network architecture (may be together with a feature based approach) can be implemented in which the orientation of the face is first determined, and then the most suitable recognition method is selected, Also the current recognition system acquires face images only from face files located on magnetic mediums. Camera and scanner support should be implemented for greater flexibility.

Conclusion:

In this study, we wished to explore the method of facial recognition using principal component analysis. We discussed the history and various applications of PCA. Following this, we described and to a small extent, demonstrated the method of PCA construction. It was shown that PCA, in a nutshell, generates orthogonal vectors that best preserve the variance (information) of a population/collection of observations of a particular random vector. It was thus proposed, that if a face image is viewed as a random vector (each pixel represents a different random variable), and if the face images were scaled and positioned similarly, then PCA is amenable to facial recognition. Experimental results have shown that, the proposed face recognition method was very sensitive to face background and head orientations. Changes in the illumination did not cause a major problem to the system. Besides, presence of small detail such as dark glasses or masks was too far from being a real challenge to the system. There exists a tradeoff between the correct recognition rate and the threshold value. As the threshold value increases, numbers of misses begin to decrease, possibly resulting in misclassifications. On the contrary, when the number of eigenfaces involved in the recognition process increases misclassification rate begins to decrease, possibly resulting in misses. The eigenface method is very sensitive to head orientations, and most of the mismatches occur for the images with large head orientations. Biometric, RFID based and so forth which are time consuming and non-efficient. So to overcome, this above framework is the better and reliable solution from every perceptive of time and security. In this way we have accomplished to add to a reliable and effective participation framework to distinguish faces of voters and recognize the faces accurately to mark the vote. The scope of the project is the system on which the software is installed, i.e. the project is developed as a desktop application, and it will work for a particular institute.

Number of Training Faces	Method	Threshold	Success Rate (Percentage)
25 (5x5)	PCA	3000	93
	LDA	500	85
	ICA	60	36
50 (10x5)	PCA	3000	79
		4000	89
		5000	93
	LDA	500	45.5
		800	67
		1000	79.5
		1200	85
	ICA	60	32
		100	32
		500	32

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